

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

MODERN DIGITAL MODELS AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS IN RECRUITING INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS TO UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract

The article concentrates on the comprehensive analysis of the education export system. The paper is based on a retrospective analysis of trends in the development of models for attracting international students and a comparative analysis of modern methods of promoting European universities that are leading in the number of international students.

Keywords. Promotion of universities, education export, comparative analysis of information strategies of universities; trends in the development of the system of attracting international applicants to universities.

One of the crucial tasks of universities is global academic leadership. In the era of the knowledge economy, education (activities of universities, first of all) is becoming an influential factor in the structure of economic growth of states. At the beginning of 2020, 5.6 million students were receiving international education, and the OECD predicts that by 2025 the number of international students will exceed 8 million [1]. Education as a form of knowledge becomes a product that brings significant income to the budgets of various countries of the world, on the one hand, and forms competition for applicants, in a broad sense, and talented young people for strategies to attract universities with a developed research perspective in countries with a high standard of living and ample opportunities for professional self-realization.

As part of the overall achievement of national educational policy goals, universities in most countries of the world have been working for several decades to achieve key indicators that correspond to priorities and make up the methodology of the QS World University Rankings and THE University Ranking, which influence the development of the international educational market. One of the distinctive features of the university's global academic leadership, reflecting the level of education exports and the degree of contribution to the digital economy, is the demand for education by applicants from abroad.

Along with achievement of high, competitive quality of educational programs, the export of education implies a second equally significant component – marketing of the university in the international educational market. It results in the relevance of this research topic on the study of the system of attracting international students.

This comparative analysis is based on a two-stage qualitative sociological study:

Stage 1. A retrospective analysis of trends in the development of the system of attracting international students allowed us to compile a set of relevant and effective promotion tools.

Stage 2. A comparative formalized content analysis of the official websites of the leading European uni-

versities in terms of the number of international students allowed us to identify which of the promotion tools are relevant and effective, which made it possible to achieve the maximum number of international students.

The object of the study is European universities. The list of universities consists of 12 universities in Austria, Germany, Great Britain, the Netherlands and Switzerland in accordance with the following criteria: in each of the studied countries there is 1 university in which 100% of students are international students, and 1 university leading the national QS ranking as of 2024 [2], as well as online universities in Europe.

The subject of research is the system of attracting international students, which have been combined into a set of tools for promoting universities to international educational markets.

The analysis of expert materials by leading researchers of the system of attracting international students allows us to identify two stages in the development of the modern education export system. The first stage (1990-2019) can be called the classical period or the period of international student mobility. The first stage is characterized by growing cross-country competition for international students (increase in the number of which is declared by many countries as national strategic goals) and predictability.

In accordance with the trends in the development of education exports of the first stage, the system of attracting international applicants was associated with a wide range of international cooperation, special international educational programs, regulatory documents regulating international student mobility, including visa loyalty programs with employment opportunities in the country of education, personalized communications and major international events (educational exhibitions, etc.). The tools used were traditional tools for attracting applicants and administrative decisions at universities.

Educational programs in English form the basis for the recruitment of international students. According to the ACA (Academic Cooperation Association), over the period 2007-2014, the growth in the number of English-language programs in universities around the world amounted to more than 200% [3].

The second stage (from 2020) in the development of the modern education export system is related to the acceleration of the development of cross-border education, institutionalization and scaling of online education formats after the COVID-19 pandemic, changes in the geopolitical situation and the revision of the partnership system in the world after 2022. This stage can be called the post-classical period or the period of education export. The trends of the second stage (fragmented practices, crowded online space, flourishing transnational education, inequality in access to technology, wealth and mobility, short international mobility experience, constant development of technology, the increasing role of employers in the education system, lifelong learning and climate change) also lead to the transformation of the university promotion system to international markets. Sales of educational services and Internet marketing are prevailing.

The international organization ICEF (International Consultants for Education and Fairs), based on the results of a survey of universities, concluded that an important trend is the growing importance of digital marketing and online promotion. 63% of universities redistribute the marketing budget in favor of online promotion.

In the study of student recruitment, a 5-step model was used, typical of the process of attracting applicants: attraction, involvement, retention, enrollment and adaptation. The set of tools for promoting educational services to international markets has become the methodological basis for comparative research using the method of formalized content analysis of official Internet sites of leading European universities in terms of the number of international students.

A common and main tool for online and traditional leader-universities to attract international students is digital solutions at the stage of attraction and their development.

Due to the specifics of providing a full range of educational services via the Internet, open universities began to master online promotion methods earlier than other universities and have now achieved the use of reliable, working tools to attract students, most often from international countries, to study using the official website.

A comparative study of the use of UX scenarios on websites revealed the following tools for effective positioning of European online universities: the main scenario is the choice of a course or application for training; a virtual open day; a detailed description of the distance learning system, including video instructions and tests to determine the applicant's ability to receive online training; free online courses as a form of testing learning opportunities; positioning of research activities at the university; video broadcasts, podcasts, popu-

lar science magazines as channels for positioning university research or career development of university graduates; reference centers; textbooks and teaching materials.

Online universities in Europe are improving their promotion in order to maximize the use of the upper level of the sales funnel – using the tools of attraction and engagement, working with the data of users involved in the selection process on the site, according to the principle of online stores.

Among the organizational decisions that make it possible to implement the tasks of these stages is the creation of at least two structural divisions at the university on the organization of attracting and adapting international students to the university, international summer schools; support for the stage of enrollment in European universities which is carried out by demonstrating detailed instructions for each stage of the registration process, submission of documents, visa-related matters, scholarships and places accommodation for the period of study, all related services and procedures.

The positioning of traditional European universities is carried out through intensive scientific and research activities, long-term and effective research programs in cooperation with the largest corporations and universities in the world. Among the main advantages, universities note the number of Nobel awarded scientists, leading world-class university research schools, ranking positions in the field of international activity, the annual number of international students and the number of countries from which students come.

Thus, the test of the developed methodology for analyzing the promotion of universities to international markets has shown the effectiveness and possibilities for further application. And it allowed us to compile and structure an initial set of university promotion tools, as well as identify relevant and promising solutions using the example of European universities.

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